

Electronic Supplementary Material

(a)

Figure S1. (a) Picture of the set-up used during indoor behavioural observations (b) The proportion of time spent on vanilla-scented vs. unscented discs for naïve control butterflies. (c,d,e) Proportion of time spent on vanilla-scented vs. unscented discs for butterflies trained with different concentrations of sinigrin as oviposition stimulus. Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used to compare differences in (b,c,d,e).

(a)

(b)

Figure S2. (a) Picture of the set-up used during outdoor behavioural observations. (b) Close up of one of the four green paper discs showing the scented filter paper and a butterfly after take-off. (c) The proportion of time spent on vanilla-scented vs. unscented discs for naïve control butterflies. (d,e,f) Proportion of time spent on vanilla-scented vs. unscented discs for butterflies trained with different concentrations of sinigrin as oviposition stimulus. Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used to compare differences in (c,d,e,f).

Table S1. Statistical results for the effects of the sinigrin concentration and the measured environmental parameters on the preference indices for the time spent on the scented discs for butterflies without a ovipositing experience and butterflies trained with different concentrations of sinigrin in an indoor setting. Analysis of deviance table (Type II Wald χ^2 - tests) for the Generalized Linear Model (GLM) with a beta-binomial. Non-significant interactions have been removed from the statistical model.

Factor	χ^2	d. f.	p-value
concentration	31.0231	3	8.406e-07
temperature	13.3936	1	0.0003
lux	0.0737	1	0.7860
baro. pressure	1.0604	1	0.3031

Table S2. Statistical results for the effects of the sinigrin concentration and the measured environmental parameters on the preference indices for the number of visits on the scented discs for butterflies without a ovipositing experience and butterflies trained with different concentrations of sinigrin in an indoor setting. Analysis of deviance table (Type II Wald χ^2 - tests) for the Generalized Linear Model (GLM) with a binomial. Non-significant interactions have been removed from the statistical model.

Factor	χ^2	d. f.	<i>p</i>-value
concentration	11.6530	3	0.0087
temperature	1.7161	1	0.1902
lux	0.0020	1	0.9648
baro. pressure	0.1598	1	0.6893

Table S3. Statistical results for the effects of the sinigrin concentration and the measured environmental parameters on the preference indices for the time spent on the scented discs for butterflies without a ovipositing experience and butterflies trained with different concentrations of sinigrin in an outdoor setting. Analysis of deviance table (Type II Wald χ^2 - tests) for the Generalized Linear Model (GLM) with a beta-binomial. Non-significant interactions have been removed from the statistical model.

Factor	χ^2	d. f.	<i>p</i>-value
concentration	3.0023	3	0.3913
temperature	0.0165	1	0.8976
lux	0.6758	1	0.4110
baro. pressure	0.0209	1	0.8851
rel. humidity	0.1858	1	0.6664
wind speed	0.4652	1	0.4952

Table S4. Statistical results for the effects of the sinigrin concentration and the measured environmental parameters on the preference indices for the number of vists on the scented discs for butterflies without a ovipositing experience and butterflies trained with different concentrations of sinigrin in an outdoor setting. Analysis of deviance table (Type II Wald χ^2 - tests) for the Generalized Linear Model (GLM) with a beta-binomial. Non-significant interactions have been removed from the statistical model.

Factor	χ^2	d. f.	<i>p</i>-value
concentration	1.5855	3	0.6627
temperature	0.2843	1	0.5939
lux	0.1172	1	0.7321
baro. pressure	0.2012	1	0.6537
rel. humidity	0.0011	1	0.9740
wind speed	0.0421	1	0.8374